

Water-in-oil microemulsion : influence of co-surfactant chain- length and nature of emulsifier[†]

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Two types of water-in-oil (w/o) microemulsions : anionic sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and cationic cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) have been studied at various temperatures (25–35°) as a function of alkyl chain-length of co-surfactant (*n*-alkanols, C₄OH–C₈OH) and oil (*n*-alkanes, C₅H–C₇H). The free energy of transfer of co-surfactant from the continuous oil phase to the interfacial region (ΔG_s^0) has been reported and the adsorption free energy per methylene group of the alkanols ($\Delta G_{s, \text{alkanol}}^0/\text{CH}_2$) has been computed. With increase in the water content the appearance of microemulsion systems changed from a clear solution to bluish which finally became turbid. The transitions were identified on the basis of specific resistance measurements. A significant change in specific resistance was observed at the transitions. The critical $n_{\text{water}}/n_{\text{oil}}$ ratio (V_c) where the microemulsion is about to breakdown, was calculated with the help of viscosity measurements.

Microemulsions were in commercial use long before^{1,2} the term was coined by Schulman *et al.*³. The most accepted definition of microemulsion is that a microemulsion is isotropic, clear or translucent, thermodynamically stable oil/water/emulsifier dispersion with or without co-solvent or co-surfactant. Extensive reviews and/or overviews are available which give the historical background and fairly up-to-date presentation of the state of our knowledge of microemulsions⁴. A number of studies have been carried out on microemulsions with alkanols as co-surfactant^{5–8}. The alkyl chain-lengths of oil and co-surfactant are known to strongly influence the interfacial composition and distribution of co-surfactant in the oil and interface^{9,10}.

Morphological changes in microemulsion systems upon dilution with water have been shown to occur by using fluorescence technique¹¹. Further, small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) studies showed the dependence of the structure of the microemulsion droplets on the alkyl chain-length of the oil phase¹². At high water content the existence of a dynamic equilibrium between the breaking and reforming of the droplets was suggested¹³. The structural factors for polydisperse droplets and phase separation in these mixtures have been simulated^{14,15}. The isotropic region in which both oil and water show rapid diffusion is often referred to as bicontinuous¹⁶. A percolation mechanism has been invoked to account for the electrical conductance of the microemulsions¹⁷. The additional surfactant increases steeply the percolation threshold in oil continuous microemulsion¹⁸.

Microemulsion structures at the molecular level are not completely described in the literature. However, there seems to be general agreement about the role of interfacial layer curvature and the importance of surfactant geometry. In all surface chemical systems where surfactant molecules are used, it has always been a practice to measure the effect of alkyl chain-length on the free energy of the system¹⁹. Even though extensive analyses on the microemulsion systems have been given in the literature, thermodynamic parameters have not been described in much detail.

Many characteristic properties of microemulsions, such as ease of formation, thermodynamic stability, high solubilizing capacity, and high penetrating ability into porous materials make these systems of interest for technical use²⁰. In recent years, water-in-oil (w/o) microemulsions have been found useful in preparing small particles (nanoparticles) of metals and inorganic salts. Microemulsions (w/o) have also been evaluated as a reaction medium^{21,22}.

As w/o type of microemulsion provides a useful system for the study of water near charged surfaces (provided by the polar groups of the surfactant), the present work reports data on the standard free energy of transfer from the continuous oil phase to the interfacial region of co-surfactant, ΔG_s^0 , as a function of temperature, alkyl chains-length of co-surfactant and oil. The structural transitions have been identified by specific resistance measurements. The critical water/oil ratio, V_c , values at which the microemulsion is about to break down (transition to multiphase system) is determined by viscosity measurements.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Results and discussion

The interfacial parameters of co-surfactant partitioning were determined by a titration study carried out according to Bowcott and Schulman²³. The plots of alcohol per mole of surfactant, n_a/n_s , versus moles of oil per mole of surfactant, n_o/n_s , should result in a straight-line with slope k and intercept I . Such plots for oil *n*-heptane-CTAB system using *n*-butanol and *n*-pentanol as co-surfactants are shown in Fig. 1. Similar plots were obtained for other oils with different combinations of SDS/CTAB-*n*-alkanols (not shown).

Fig. 1 shows that the temperature increase hardly affects the value of slope k while the intercept I decreases considerably. The parallelism of the plots indicates that the solubi-

per mole for the adsorption of alkanol was calculated from the equation,

$$\Delta G_s^0 = -RT \ln x_a^i/x_a^o \quad (1)$$

The values of ΔG_s^0 at different temperatures for various surfactant-co-surfactant-oil combinations are given in Table 1. The ΔG_s^0 values are found to be negative in all the systems which suggests that the association between emulsifier and co-surfactant increases with increase in the chain-length of *n*-alkanols in all the oils and surfactants studied. This is in conformity with the earlier findings^{5,24}. Also, when SDS is used as an emulsifier the values of ΔG_s^0 become less negative as we proceed from C₅H to C₇H. This indicates that the association between emulsifier and co-surfactant is becoming

Fig. 1. Plots of moles of *n*-alkanol per mole of surfactant (n_a/n_s) vs moles of oil per mole of surfactant (n_o/n_s) for microemulsions composed of CTAB (1 g)-water (1 g)-*n*-pentanol-*n*-alkanol at different temperatures.

lity of the co-surfactant in the oil phase does not change in the temperature range used. The fact that the solubility of alkanol in the continuous phase remains unaltered and that the number of moles of alkanol per mole of surfactant decrease with temperature, could be explained on the basis that, at higher temperature, more alkanol molecules in presence of surfactant are transferred into the aqueous water pool. No doubt the amount of alkanol transferred from the interface into the water phase would depend on the nature of co-surfactant, oil and the emulsifier.

A linear regression program was used to fit the data (Fig. 1): slope k (moles of alkanol per mole of oil) and intercept, I (moles of alkanol per mole of surfactant at zero moles of oil) were determined. From the I and k values, the mole fraction of alcohol in the interphase, x_a^i , and in the oil phase, x_a^o , were calculated as done earlier⁸. The free energy change

weaker with increase in the chain-length of oil phase. On the other hand, when CTAB is used as the emulsifier, no definite trend in ΔG_s^0 values are obtained. Table 1 also shows that ΔG_s^0 values are more negative for CTAB microemulsion than the SDS one and indicates stronger association between CTAB-co-surfactant than SDS-co-surfactant. These factors could be understood by considering the droplet structural differences that exist as a consequence of head group size and steric requirements. Since a positive charge resides on the quaternary nitrogen atom of CTAB, the microemulsion droplet is less exposed than the negatively charged droplet of SDS; as a result, it increases interactions of CTAB with the co-surfactant and therefore ΔG_s^0 decreases for the case. The higher association of co-surfactants with CTAB could also be understood by the fact that *n*-alkanols are slightly deprotonated which assist the co-surfactant to associate

Table 1. Variation of ΔG_s^0 with temperature for *n*-alkanols in the microemulsions composed of surfactant (1 g), water (1 g), *n*-alkane and *n*-alkanol

<i>n</i> -Alkanol	$-\Delta G_s^0$ for SDS (kJ mol ⁻¹)								
	<i>n</i> -Pentane			<i>n</i> -Hexane			<i>n</i> -Heptane		
	25°	30°	35°	25°	30°	35°	25°	30°	35°
<i>n</i> -Butanol	5.46	5.52	5.69	5.12	5.19	5.10	4.87	4.86	4.84
<i>n</i> -Pentanol	6.17	6.19	6.19	5.82	5.83	5.98	5.61	5.68	5.81
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	6.57	6.61	6.64	6.34	6.32	6.33	5.94	5.95	6.03
<i>n</i> -Alkanol	$-\Delta G_s^0$ for CTAB (kJ mol ⁻¹)								
	25°	30°	35°	25°	30°	35°	25°	30°	35°
	<i>n</i> -Butanol	6.47	6.53	6.55	6.87	6.90	7.02	6.17	6.31
<i>n</i> -Pentanol	7.24	7.33	7.35	–	7.17	7.31	6.39	6.55	–
<i>n</i> -Hexanol	7.71	7.87	7.92	8.35	8.57	8.80	7.25	7.34	8.15
<i>n</i> -Heptanol	8.42	8.50	8.71	8.70	8.96	9.04	8.80	8.91	9.04
<i>n</i> -Octanol	8.92	9.13	9.21	9.39	9.52	9.82	9.24	9.36	9.50

strongly with cationic CTAB than with anionic SDS. This fact also explains as why quaternary ammonium salt microemulsions solubilize more water than anionic surfactant systems²⁵.

Table 2 summarizes the values of free energy change per methylene group of the alkanol, $\Delta G_{s,alkanol}^0/CH_2$, for different oil phases (for comparison, value for benzene, calculated from literature data⁹, is also included in the table). Quite contrary reports have appeared regarding the effect of alkyl chain-length of alkanols on ΔG_s^0 ^{9,24}. We have also explored the effect and found ΔG_s^0 to decrease linearly with the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain of the co-surfactant. Similar trend was observed earlier⁵. It is clear from Table 2 that $\Delta G_{s,alkanol}^0/CH_2$ values are much lower for C₅H to C₇H as compared to benzene. This indicates that the energetics of transfer of alkanol from oil phase to interfacial region would depend on the structure of both these phases. Even if the standard chemical potential of alcohol is assumed to be much the same in the two oil phases, differences would exist as regards to the standard chemical potential of alkanol in the interfacial regions. The interfa-

Table 2. Variation of $\Delta G_{s,alkanol}^0/CH_2$ at different temperatures for different oils for SDS- and CTAB-microemulsions

Hydrocarbon	$-\Delta G_{s,alkanol}^0/CH_2$ (SDS)			$-\Delta G_{s,alkanol}^0/CH_2$ (CTAB)		
	J mol ⁻¹			J mol ⁻¹		
	25°	30°	35°	25°	30°	35°
<i>n</i> -Pentane	555	545	475	–	637	668
<i>n</i> -Hexane	610	565	615	618	703	733
<i>n</i> -Heptane	535	545	595	855	846	699
Benzene	218 ^a	–	–	–	–	–

*Ref. 9.

cial region with benzene would be expected to be at higher energy than the present oil phases. This would again mean that the change in ΔG_s^0 with increasing number of carbon atoms in alkanol would be less prominent in benzene as oil phase than in *n*-alkane. The $\Delta G_{s,alkanol}^0/CH_2$ values roughly range from – 500 to – 850 J mol⁻¹ CH₂. This values is in agreement with the value 840 J mol⁻¹ CH₂ obtained from the data reported earlier⁵. The slight difference may be due to the different emulsifier (sodium stearate) and oil phase (*n*-hexadecane) used⁵. This could be understood on the basis that transfer of alkanol is dependent on the structure of oil phase and the nature of interfacial region.

It has been found that ΔG_s^0 changes linearly with the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain of the oil phase. Calculated values of free energy change per methylene group, $\Delta G_{s,oil}^0/CH_2$, of the oil phase are summarized in Table 3 for different SDS/co-surfactant combinations. The values roughly range 200–400 J mol⁻¹ CH₂, which are in close agreement with the reported values^{8,10,24}.

Table 3. Variation of $\Delta G_{s,oil}^0/CH_2$ at different temperatures for different *n*-alkanols in SDS-microemulsions

<i>n</i> -Alkanol	$\Delta G_{s,oil}^0/CH_2$		
	J mol ⁻¹		
	25°	30°	35°
<i>n</i> -Butanol	295	330	425
<i>n</i> -Pentanol	280	255	190
<i>n</i> -Heptanol	315	330	305

Fig. 2 shows the specific resistance of C₅OH microemulsions as a function of alkyl chain-length of the oil phase at different water/oil ratios. From different transitions shown in this figure and also from the visual appearance of systems, it has been observed that, with increase in water content, all systems pass through clear to bluish to turbid regions. The initial decrease in resistance with SDS and an increase with CTAB in the optically clear region suggests that contribution due to surface conductance increases with water/oil ratio in SDS systems and decreases in CTAB systems to the effective volume conductivity²⁶. It was further observed that after a certain water/oil ratio, the specific resistance falls abruptly with a further increase in the water/oil ratio. The abrupt drop in specific resistance in bluish region could be due to a transition in the droplet structure from that of spheres to cylinders to lamellae leading to phase separation. The formation of such structures would decrease the specific resistance since the ions could move through water droplet cylinders to lamellae without passing through the oil/water

Fig. 2. Plots of specific resistance vs moles of water per mole of oil ($n_{\text{water}}/n_{\text{oil}}$) for microemulsions composed of surfactant (1 g)-water-oil (20 ml)-*n*-pentanol (5 ml) at 30°: (—) clear region, (----) bluish region, (.....) turbid region.

Fig. 3. Variation of viscosity (η) against $n_{\text{water}}/n_{\text{oil}}$ of microemulsions composed of surfactant (1 g)-water-oil (20 ml)-*n*-pentanol (5 ml) at 30°.

interfacial region⁵. At constant water/oil ratio, the specific resistance was found to decrease with increase in the oil chain-length which suggests that conducting microemulsions are produced with higher chain-length alkanes⁶. This observation is in agreement with earlier findings⁶. It was further observed that with SDS/C₅OH system there is a steep fall in specific resistance within a narrow range of water/oil ratio. This sharp decrease after certain water/oil

ratio may be due to the phenomenon of percolation¹⁷. This phenomenon has been considered to be due to the charge transport from one droplet to another by 'transient droplet fusion' mechanism²⁷. Accordingly, one can view the increase in oil chain-length in the microemulsion to enhance the percolation phenomenon, resulting in a decrease in the electrical resistance.

The V_c values at which the microemulsion is about to

Fig. 4. Plots of V_c ($n_{\text{water}}/n_{\text{oil}}$) against surfactant concentration (g/20 ml of oil) in microemulsion at 30°.

break have been obtained from viscosity versus $n_{\text{water}}/n_{\text{oil}}$ plots (Fig. 3). We see that, at a particular water/oil ratio, the viscosity increases with the chain-length of oil for both SDS and CTAB. This clearly indicates that larger droplets are formed with the higher chain-length alkanes. Further, the V_c values were higher for CTAB- than for SDS-microemulsions. This phenomenon could be explained in the light of surfactant-co-surfactant interactions. Lower ΔG_s^0 values for CTAB systems than for SDS (Table 1) indicate that oil/water interface is more stable for CTAB-microemulsions : this being the reason of higher V_c values for CTAB-microemulsions.

Subsequent plots of V_c values vs gram surfactant per 20 ml oil resulted in straight-lines (Fig. 4.) The number of moles of water per mole of surfactant at the critical ratio where the microemulsions remain stable have been calculated from the slopes of these plots. The same value of slope has been found for different oils which depends upon the nature of emulsifier. Higher values for the CTAB systems again confirm the viewpoint that the CTAB- microemulsions could accommodate higher number of water molecules than the SDS systems, as suggested earlier²⁵.

It can be concluded that microemulsions of different oil phases are stabilized by various interfacial forces, since the variation of ΔG_s^0 with increasing number of carbon atoms in *n*-alkanols and *n*-alkanes is different. It has also been concluded that with CTAB, microemulsions of large water-pool would be formed.

Experimental

Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, 99%) and cetyltrimethyl-ammonium bromide (CTAB, 99%) (Fluka), *n*-pentane (C_5H) (E. Merck, 99%), *n*-hexane (C_6H , 99%), *n*-heptane (C_7H , 99%) and all alkanols (C_4OH - C_8OH) (all B.D.H.) were used as supplied. Double-distilled water (sp. cond. $(1-2) \times 10^{-6}$

$S \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was used throughout the work. The measurements were carried out at fixed temperatures ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) maintained in a thermostated bath.

The method of preparation of microemulsions was the same as described earlier¹⁰. At constant temperature, a coarse emulsion was first produced by appropriate mixing of the surfactant (1 g), water (1 g) and oil (20 ml). This mixture was then titrated with a co-surfactant to obtain a clear solution (microemulsion). More oil was then added which turned the system turbid. The turbid mixture was further titrated with co-surfactant until it became transparent. The process was repeated to obtain several experimental points. The studies were carried out at different temperatures (25–35°) with each oil and alkanol. To prepare microemulsions of various compositions, the amount of water was varied in the each set of experiments. All the systems were stable and no phase separation took place after keeping them for weeks. Also, the electrical resistance and viscosity of the microemulsion system of a given composition did not change with time.

Electrical resistance was measured by a Philips PR 9500 conductivity meter equipped with platinized electrodes (cell constant, 0.51 cm^{-1}). Viscosity was measured by a Ubbelohde viscometer thermostated at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Density was determined using a precalibrated dilatometer.

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